

Table A1. Biological process categories for 16 genes.

For up-regulated DEGs

GO:0035610 protein side chain deglutamylation (Agbl2,p-value=1.57e-03)
GO:0035608 protein deglutamylation (Agbl2,p-value=2.2e-03)
GO:0009790 embryo development (Alx3,Dusp2,Pcdh12,p-value=2.88e-03)
GO:0016339 calcium-dependent cell-cell adhesion via plasma membrane cell adhesion molecules (Pcdh12,p-value=5.64e-03)
GO:0000188 inactivation of MAPK activity (Dusp2, p-value=6.26e-03)
GO:0018200 peptidyl-glutamic acid modification (Agbl2,p-value=6.89e-03)
GO:0048568 embryonic organ development (Alx3,Pcdh12,p-value=8.19e-03)
GO:0035116 embryonic hindlimb morphogenesis(Alx3,p-value=9.389e-03)
GO:0035115 embryonic forelimb morphogenesis(Alx3,p-value=1.0689e-03)
GO:0035137 hindlimb morphogenesis (Alx3,p-value=1.1989e-03)

For down-regulated DEGs

GO:0032792 negative regulation of CREB transcription factor activity (Adgrg3, p-value=2.2e-03)
GO:1901223 negative regulation of NIK/NF-kappaB signaling (Adgrg3, p-value=2.56e-03)
GO:0035376 sterol import (Stard5, p-value= 2.93e-03)
GO:0070508 cholesterol import (Stard5, p-value=2.93e-03)
GO:2001135 regulation of endocytic recycling (Ehd2, p-value=2.93e-03)
GO:0006390 transcription from mitochondrial promoter (Tefm, p-value=4.75e-03)
GO:0097320 membrane tubulation (Ehd2, p-value=5.12e-03)
GO:1901741 positive regulation of myoblast fusion (Ehd2, p-value=6.94e-03)
GO:1901739 regulation of myoblast fusion (Ehd2, p-value=7.67e-03)
GO:0060143 positive regulation of syncytium formation by plasma membrane fusion (Ehd2, p-value=9.12e-03)